

Connections between bullying victimization and satisfaction/frustration of the basic psychological needs

Abstract

The aim of this study is to analyse the connection between bullying and the dichotomy satisfaction-frustration of the basic psychological needs in adolescents. A total of 1845 students from Secondary Education (928 boys and 917 girls), and Baccalaureate-Year 1 ($n = 278$), aged between 12 and 17 ($M = 14.51$, $DT = 1.55$), from 16 schools of four Spanish provinces participate in the study. Students complete the *Psychological Needs Satisfaction-Frustration Scale* and the subscale *Victimization* from the *European Bullying Intervention Project Questionnaire* concerning three subjects: Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature and Physical Education. Results from the structural equation analysis reflect that victimization negatively predicts the satisfaction of the three basic psychological needs of competence, relatedness and autonomy, and positively the frustration of them in the three subjects. These results show the importance of creating educative contexts oriented to promote an increase of the students' basic psychological needs of autonomy, relatedness and competence to prevent and/or lessen the possible effects of bullying in their victims.

Keywords: bullying; frustration/satisfaction; psychological needs, Secondary Education, adolescence.

Introduction

Nowadays, bullying is one of the most important problems that educational practitioners have to face. Therefore, in recent years a significant number of scientific productions have emerged addressing this problem (Albayrak, Yildiz and Erol, 2016; Bondu, Rothmund and Gollwitzer, 2016). Cepeda-Cuervo, Pacheco-Durán, García-Barco, and Piraquive-Peña (2009, p. 518) point out that bullying is “a type of violence that is manifested by repeated psychological, physical or social aggressions suffered by a child in the school environment by their classmates.” It is important to differentiate between school violence and bullying. While bullying has a repeated and continued nature, school violence does not necessarily have to have that persistent aspect (Fialho and Bakshi, 2016; Graham, 2016; Menéndez and Fernández-Río, 2018). For example, when a student in class performs a sporadic violent behaviour on another classmate, it does not have to be bullying, unless that behaviour is continued over time. In recent years, with the rise of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), a new type of bullying appears: cyberbullying, which involves repeatedly harassing an individual through technological means (Garaigordobil, 2014; Garaigordobil and Martínez-Valderrey, 2015). Authors such as Garaibordobil (2014) state that between 40% and 55% of schoolchildren are involved in this type of bullying, either as victims or as aggressors, hence the crucial relevance of this type of bullying in the current paradigm educational.

Bullying is understood as violent behaviour among equals characterized by its intentionality, persistence and imbalance of power (Olweus, 2005). It has been analyzed from different points of view, although one of the most studied is that of the double profile: aggression vs victimization (Magaz, Chorot, Santed, Valiente and Sandín, 2016). Bullying as aggression is described as the situation in which an individual exercises continuous negative behaviours on another individual, while victimization deals with the opposite situation: a person experiences persistent negative behaviours by one or several

partners (Bondu et al., 2016; Harbin, Kelley, Piscitello, and Walker, 2019). León-Moreno, Martínez-Ferrer, Musitu and Ochoa (2019) analyse the relationship between school violence and victimization, considering the motivation for revenge, avoidance and benevolence in a sample of 671 adolescents between 10 and 16 years. The results reflect a clear positive relationship between victimization and school violence, both direct and indirect. Likewise, victimization is also linked to avoidance motivation and benevolence, since the predictors of victimization are several. Cook, Williams, Guerra, Kim and Sadek (2010) conduct a meta-analysis of 153 studies linked to bullying and find as individual predictors of victimization variables such as peer status, social competence or academic performance. The meta-analysis also reflects that victimization is clearly related to other variables of great importance such as school climate or family environment. A more recent meta-analysis (Schoeler, Duncan, Ploubidis, Cecis and Pingault, 2018) of research with quasi-experimental designs shows that victimization is related in the short term to well-being, anxiety and depression. These results are supported by recent ones such as the one carried out by Miranda, Oriol Amutio and Ortúzar (2019) in a sample of 5774 schoolchildren, which reflects that the support received by parents at home helps to reduce the inverse relationship so substantive existing between victimization and satisfaction with life. All elements that are related to victimization, such as depression, anxiety or life satisfaction in people who suffer bullying, can lead directly to school dropout, as reported by authors such as Hutzell and Payne (2018).

In the last three decades, one of the most used frames of reference to study and understand the motivation of individuals in the school context is the Theory of Self-Determination (Ryan and Deci, 2002). It states that people have three innate and universal needs that have a decisive influence on their motivational behaviour and psychological well-being: a) Autonomy: intentional and self-referenced behaviour; b) Competence: feeling of effective interaction with the context and having experiences to show one's own abilities; c) Relationship: feeling of being included and being taken care of by others. The satisfaction of these three needs is associated with high levels of self-determined motivation, since they mediate the effects of socio-contextual factors such as the teacher or classmates (Vallerand, 2001). Recently, the frustration of these basic psychological needs emerges as a construct that does not simply represent a simple lack of satisfaction of them (Vansteenkiste and Ryan, 2013), but is related differently with similar variables. The research shows how the satisfaction of needs predicts positive consequences such as intrinsic motivation, while their frustration predicts negative consequences such as negative affect (Longo, Gunz, Curtis, and Farsides, 2016). Therefore, current research seems to opt for using this double construct of frustration-satisfaction of the basic psychological needs for the study of the motivation of individuals.

Research about the connection between basic psychological needs and bullying in the educational context is scarce. Young-Jones, Fursa, Byrket and Sly (2015) study this relationship in 130 high school and university students, finding that those who point out that they are victims of bullying, both past and present, have less academic motivation. In addition, those who were victims had significantly lower levels of autonomy and competence. On the other hand, Hein, Koka, and Hagger (2015) study the relationship between the frustration of basic psychological needs, anger, bullying and the teacher's controlling behaviour in secondary school students. They find that students' perception of this type of behaviour is indirectly related to anger and bullying through a frustration of basic psychological needs. That is, their frustration may be related to feelings of anger, which in turn relate to aggressive behaviours with other students such as bullying.

So far, there are no published studies that analyse the frustration-satisfaction dichotomy connection of basic psychological needs with bullying. This could be the first

study that analyses this connection in high school students. Based on previous research that indicates: a) a positive and significant correlation between the frustration of basic psychological needs and bullying (Hein et al. (2015), b) that the frustration of these needs is associated with negative behaviours such as depression or anxiety (Mehdipour, Gholamali, and Hejazi, 2016), variables closely linked to victimization behaviours (Forbes, Fitzpatrick, Magson, and Rapee, 2019), and c) that victimized individuals suffer a deterioration of their basic psychological needs (Harbin et al., 2019), the main objective of this research is to analyse the predictive power of victimization on the satisfaction-frustration dichotomy of the psychological needs of autonomy, relationship and competence in three different curricular subjects of Secondary Education: Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature and Physical Education. Taking the above as a reference, the following hypothesis is proposed (H1): victimization predicts in a negative way the satisfaction of the three basic psychological needs and in a positive way the frustration of them.

Method

Design and participants

An ex post facto prospective cross-sectional and correlational research design is used (Bisquerra, 2012). A total of 1845 students (928 men and 917 women), from Secondary Education (1st grade, n = 406; 2nd grade, n = 390; 3rd grade, n = 364, 4th grade, n = 407) and Baccalaureate (1st grade, n = 278), aged between 12 and 17 years old (M = 14.51, SD = 1.55), of a total of 16 high schools in three areas of Spain: north (Asturias), north-central (León) and south-central (Cuenca and Albacete) participate in the study. 597 answer the questionnaire referring to the Mathematics subject, 600 the one referring to the subject of Spanish Language and Literature, and 648 the one referring to the Physical Education subject. All schools have a medium socioeconomic level, between 400 and 700 students, and offer Compulsory Secondary Education and Baccalaureate. The researchers do not have any type of relationship with the students of the high schools.

Procedure

For the development of the present research, the permission of the Ethics Committee of the University of the different authors of the work is obtained first. Subsequently, the research team contacts the management teams of the different participating high schools to request their collaboration. Families are subsequently informed of the objectives of the study and informed consent is obtained from all those interested in their children participating in the project. After that, the researchers, in each of their areas of residence, administer the questionnaires over approximately 20 minutes, indicating that the answers are completely anonymous and that in no case do they influence their qualifications. All researchers follow the same protocol in the different high schools.

Instruments

Satisfaction-frustration of basic psychological needs. The Spanish version of the Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction and Frustration Scale (BPNSFS; Longo, Alcaraz-Ibáñez and Sicilia, 2018) is used. This includes six subscales that measure the three needs: *autonomy, relationship and competence* and for each need, three subscales assess the

satisfaction and frustration of each of them through three items: *autonomy satisfaction* (e.g., “I feel that I have freedom to do things”), *relationship satisfaction* (e.g., “I feel that I care about the people around me”), *competence satisfaction* (e.g., “I feel that I am quite good at what I do”), *autonomy frustration* (e.g., “I feel obligated to perform tasks in a certain way”), *relationship frustration* (e.g., “I feel that sometimes others exclude me”) and *competence frustration* (e.g., “I doubt of being able to properly perform my tasks”). The questionnaire is preceded by the heading: “In my studies of ...” followed by one of the three subjects in which the variables are measured: “Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature or Physical Education”. All items are scored on a Likert response scale from one (strongly disagree) to seven (strongly agree). Reliability estimates for BPNSFS subscales range between .79 and .85 for *autonomy satisfaction*, .72 and .77 for *relationship satisfaction*, .75 and .85 for *competence satisfaction*, .69 and .80 for *autonomy frustration*, .74 and .79 for *relationship frustration* and .74 and .80 for *competence frustration* (Longo et al., 2018).

Bullying. The *victimization* subscale of the *European Bullying Intervention Project Questionnaire*, prepared by Brighi et al. (2012) and validated in Spanish by Ortega, del Rey and Casas (2016). It is made up of seven items (e.g., “Someone has hit me, kicked me or pushed me”). All items have a Likert design, with a score between zero (never) and four (always), referring to a time interval of the last two months. Cronbach's alpha in the original scale is .80.

Analysis of data

Confirmatory factor analyses of the hypothesized models are carried out, since they had not been validated either in the context used (different secondary school subjects), or for these formative ages (12-17 years). For this, the EQS 6.1 software is used. Subsequently, analyses of structural equations are performed in which the victimization factor predicts the six dimensions of basic psychological needs. Preliminary analyses show a lack of multivariate normality, so it is decided to use the chi-square Satorra-Bentler statistic (S-B χ^2) and robust standard estimators. The goodness of the data adjustment is determined by the following criteria (Byrne, 2008): * CFI (Comparative Fit Index) as an incremental adjustment index and * RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error Approximation) and SRMR (Root Mean Square Residual) as absolute adjustment index measures. To determine the goodness of the fit, the appropriate cut-off criteria are chosen (Hu and Bentler, 1999) and attention is paid to whether the results approach or exceed the rigorous limits (indicated in brackets): $\chi^2 / df \leq 2.0$; $IFC \geq .90$ (.95); $SRMR \leq .08$ (.07); $RMSEA \leq .10$ (.06).

Results

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Goodness of fit indexes are calculated for the three samples separately and the two proposed models (Table 1). In all three samples, the BPNSFS scale shows optimal adjustment rates (Byrne 2006; Kline 2005). The victimization subscale, also in the three samples, does not reach acceptable levels of goodness of fit, so it is re-specified. The modification indices (Jöreskog and Sörbom, 1984), for items V1 and V3 show an estimate of the amount by which the discrepancy function would decrease if the analysis were repeated with the restrictions in that deleted parameter, so they are eliminated. The re-

specified victimization scale with five items shows optimal adjustment rates in the three samples.

Table 1. Goodness of fit indexes in Confirmatory Factor Analysis and in hypothetical models.

	x ² /df	*CFI	*RMSEA	SRMR
Mathematics				
BPNSFS	1.59	.987	.031 (.023 - .040)	.033
Victimization	4.70	.857	.079 (.060 - .098)	.058
Re-Specified Victimization	1.68	.981	.034 (.000 - .072)	.031
Hypothetical model	1.76	.972	.036 (.030 - .042)	.043
Spanish Language and Literature				
BPNSFS	1.56	.987	.031 (.022 - .039)	.034
Victimization	8.29	.784	.110 (.092 - .129)	.064
Re-Specified Victimization	1.03	.999	.007 (.000 - .058)	.021
Hypothetical model	1.70	.973	.034 (.028 - .040)	.044
Physical Education				
BPNSFS	1.72	.984	.033 (.026 - .041)	.033
Victimization	4.49	.853	.073 (.055 - .092)	.059
Re-Specified Victimization	1,26	1.00	.000 (.000 - .021)	.008
Hypothetical model	1.81	.968	.036 (.030 - .041)	.040

Descriptive analysis and bivariate correlations

The results analysed through Cronbach's alpha are, in all cases, adequate. The highest scores are observed, in the three samples, in the relationship satisfaction variable and the lowest victimization scores. The highest correlations appear, in negative, among the satisfaction / frustration of the same basic psychological need. The victimization variable correlates significantly in a negative way with the satisfaction of the three basic psychological needs, and in a positive way with the frustration of the same needs (Table 2).

Table 2. Cronbach alphas, omega values, descriptive analyses and bivariate correlations among all variables.

Mathematics										
	α (IC 95%)	ω	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Autonomy Satisfaction	.93 (.94-.94)	.93	4.43	1.73	1					
2. Relationship satisfaction	.86 (.84-.88)	.87	5.60	1.26	.30**	1				
3. Competence Satisfaction	.91 (.90-.92)	.92	4.56	1.46	.37**	.34**	1			
4. Autonomy Frustration	.88 (.87-.90)	.89	3.47	1.66	-.47**	-.14**	-.16**	1		
5. Relationship Frustration	.89 (.88-.91)	.90	1.91	1.26	-.16**	-.55**	-.16**	.22**	1	
6. Competence Frustration	.88 (.87-.90)	.88	2.71	1.54	-.29**	-.25**	-.56**	.33**	.38**	1
7. Victimization	.70 (.67-.74)	.73	1.39	.44	-.16**	-.31**	-.22**	.16**	.41**	.29**
Spanish Language and Literature										
	α	ω	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Autonomy Satisfaction	.91 (.90-.92)	.91	4.84	1.52	1					
2. Relationship satisfaction	.88 (.86-.90)	.88	5.58	1.30	.20**	1				
3. Competence Satisfaction	.87 (.85-.88)	.87	4.83	1.24	.30**	.40**	1			
4. Autonomy Frustration	.86 (.83-.87)	.86	3.32	1.53	-.36**	-.10*	-.17**	1		
5. Relationship Frustration	.90 (.89-.91)	.91	1.96	1.26	-.13**	-.57**	-.24**	.21**	1	
6. Competence Frustration	.87 (.84-.88)	.86	2.36	1.31	-.20**	-.29**	-.54**	.26**	.48**	1

7. Victimization	.75 (.72-.78)	.75	1.42	.48	-.18**	-.47**	-.19**	.19**	.52**	.30**
Physical Education										
	α	ω	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Autonomy Satisfaction	.92 (.91-.93)	.92	4.65	1.60	1					
2. Relationship satisfaction	.88 (.86-.90)	.88	5.69	1.21	.36**	1				
3. Competence Satisfaction	.91 (.89-.92)	.91	4.88	1.33	.28**	.44**	1			
4. Autonomy Frustration	.86 (.84-.88)	.86	3.24	1.45	-.41**	-.20**	-.11**	1		
5. Relationship Frustration	.90 (.89-.92)	.90	1.77	1.14	-.15**	-.64**	-.24**	.21**	1	
6. Competence Frustration	.87 (.85-.88)	.86	2.30	1.28	-.17**	-.37**	-.57**	.28**	.42**	1
7. Victimization	.72 (.69-.76)	.71	1.36	.45	-.23**	-.41**	-.13**	.20**	.47**	.28**

Analyse of structural equation models

In the three samples, the same model in which *victimization* variable predicts significantly six dimensions of the basic psychological needs is tested (Figure 1).

The adjustment of the theoretical model is, in every case, optimum. The explained variance ranges between .03 and .66. The higher predictable value is for *victimization* variable over *relationship frustration* variable for all the cases, whit R^2 values among .51 and .66. *Victimization* variable has the higher predictive value over *relationship frustration* variable in all the cases, with R^2 values among .51 and .66. The victimization variable predicts negatively the satisfaction of three of the basic psychological needs and positively the frustration of the same needs, which shows a negative impact in the psychological needs of the three analysed school subjects: Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature, and Physical Education.

Last, a multi-sample SEM analyse is conducted to confirm whether the samples are matched-samples or not in the field of the theoretical model.

Figure 1. Hypothetical model in the three samples.

Note: values for each simple are presented upright in this order: Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature and Physical Education;

Multi-sample analyse

The measurement invariance or factorial equivalence point how far the presented model has the same meaning for different groups (Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature, and Physical Education). The checked invariance in the causal analyse is linked to the imposition of restrictions in the model. Thus, it have run an invariance *multistep* analyse (Byrne, 2008). First, the initial model has been analysed without restrictions, which has defined the start point for subsequent comparisons with other models (Marsh and Bryme, 1993). Then, it is forced the structural weights to stay invariable. For the next step, also covariance are kept steady forcedly. Last stage restricts

too the structural residuals. The results evidence that compared models present acceptable adjustment index (Table 3). As the coefficient χ^2 is sensitive to the sample size, values for ΔCFI less than or equal to -.01 it has used as criteria to indicate that invariance null hypothesis cannot be rejected (Cheung and Rensvold, 2002). In that case the biggest difference is -.004, which suggests that the structure is, largely, invariant in the three analysed samples. These results provide a strong support for the proposed model. Therefore, the effects that the subject (Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature, and Physical Education) has above different causal relationships within the explicative model are very moderate.

Tabla 3. Model 1 = without restrictions; Model 2 = structural invariant weights; Model 3 = invariant structural covariance; Model 4 = invariant residual structural.

Model	S-B χ^2	df	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δgl	*CFI	SRMR	*RMSEA (90% CI)
M ₁	1102.51	627	-	-	.971	.043	.034 (.032 – .039)
M ₂	1117.18	639	14.67	12	.971	.045	.035 (.031 – .038)
M ₃	1170.42	669	53.24	30	.969	.055	.035 (.032 – .038)
M ₄	1273.33	727	102.91	58	.967	.060	.035 (.032 – .038)

Discussion

The basic aim of the present study is to evaluate the predictable power of *victimization* above the dichotomy satisfaction-frustration from basic psychological needs of *autonomy*, *relationship* and *competence* in the different curricular subjects belonged to Secondary Education: Mathematics, Spanish Language and Literature, and Physical Education. The results indicate that *victimization* variable predicts negatively the satisfaction of these three basic psychological needs and positively the frustration of these same needs. That relation keeps invariable in the three curricular subjects analysed.

In spite of there are not known researches which analyse the dichotomy satisfaction-frustration of the basic psychological needs and bully scholar behaviour for Secondary students at once, researches from authors like Hein et al. (2015), point a positively and significant correlation between the frustration of the basic psychological needs and scholar harassment in a similar target population like in this study is presented. That result supports widely the findings described in this research. Consequently with the scientific literature and the Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Deci, 2002) this show that the satisfaction of the basic psychological needs is distinctly related with adaptative behaviours as intrinsic motivation (Huhtiniemi, Sääkslahti, Watt and Jaakkola, 2019) or social responsibility (Menéndez and Fernández-Río, 2017). These mentioned behaviours are essentials to build a positive classroom climate and lessen aggressive attitudes. Whereas, the frustration of that needs use to be allied to negative perceived behaviours like depression or anxiety (Mehdipour et al., 2016) that are variables tightly related with *victimization* behaviors as scientific literature reports (Forbes et al., 2019). For that reason, the results in the present study indicate that people who are scholar bullying victims, which are victimized, who experience negative behaviour from one or more fellows (Bondu et al. 2016; Harbin et al., 2019), they suffer impairment of their basic psychological needs of competence, autonomy and relationship; with all the negative impacts identified by scientific literature: motivation drop, depression or anxiety. Hence, all victimized students (or under suspect to be) have to be helped to recover from the frustration of their basic psychological needs through educative programs “to promote the socio-emotional develop to improve and prevent / reduce violence, because the best way to avoid the violence is to build up the coexistence” (Garaigordobil and Martinez-Valderrey, 2014, p. 300).

More can be said from a depth analysis for each one of the basic psychological needs evaluated. About *relationship*: a student who suffers bullying will have frustrated his or her need to relate with the other pals (feels value and integrated into a group as well as close to other students). As a matter of fact, the results in this study express that the biggest predictive value of *victimization* is above the frustration of the *relationship* variable. Therefore, relations among peers play a central role in bullying cases. In that line, it is important to highlight that bullies are deeply immersed with a phenomenon known as “homophily” (Van Ryzin and Roseth, 2018) and they use to relate exclusively with mates who see aggression such as normal (Brechtwald and Prinstein, 2011). The similarities are reinforced when people are grouped under a same profile, perpetuating even more the bully behavior. Due to that, the victims are isolated from other classmates while in class and, subsequently, they feel highly frustrated their *relationship* need. When the students are harassed, victimized, they fall in a negative spiral where they begin to feel embarrassment, self-compassion and self-blame, and they cope the conflict through completely passive strategies (Caurcel and Almeida, 2008). As a result, the victimized cycle is perpetuated even more and leads to bullies to think that victims are not capable to control the situation. Consequently, the aggression is more often done causing the school bullying issue and the victim is more and more isolated.

Other researchers that shows that students with more social ties are less likely bullying victims support this (Hodges, Malone, and Perry, 1997; Kendrick, Jutengren, and Stattin, 2012). Thereupon from the result of the present study show that the relationship need has to be reinforced in the school context, especially to prevent and/or diminish the negative effects of the victimization. Previous studies have demonstrated how innovative teaching approaches based on pedagogical models as Personal and Social Responsibility Model or the Sport Education Model allow to rise the relationship among students (Menéndez and Fernández-Rio, 2016), because these models propose working in small groups where the aid behavior is necessary and mandatory while the role is rotary (e.g., captain, coach, etc.).

In addition, the development of the responsibility includes levels of work like helping behaviour. Also, Cooperative Learning is another model which has the main aim to tackle the development of the interpersonal abilities (e.g., to share, to listen, to keep to your turn...) that help to connect at a social level and it matches perfectly with the Personal and Social responsibility Model (Fernández-Rio, 2014).

About *competence* need: the results have shown that *victimization* variable predicts positively the frustration but negatively the satisfaction of this need. Having Young-Jones et al. (2015) in account, the results are partially supported in his previous research where they studied the relation between basic psychological needs and school bullying inside of a school context. They found that students who informed to be victims (both in the past and in the present) have lower academic motivation and significantly lower competence levels. These low academic and competence levels lead those students to be seen as clearly targets by bullies. For that reason, these victimized students grow their psychological stress, which cross cutting affects their academic achievement, and as a result, their competence perceived (Juvonen, Nishina, and Graham, 2000). In other hand, if a student has a well perception of his or her competence, is going to be more intrinsically motivated, and because of that, following the line marked by the results under the frame of the Self-Determination Theory, is going to have bigger adaptive behaviours: more self-esteem, more socialize ability, etc. (Sánchez-Oliva, Viladrich, Amado, González-Ponce, and García-Calvo, 2014). So, in light of the results, it becomes necessary to improve the competence level of all the students to prevent and/or diminish the negative effects of the victimization. Once again, pedagogical models as that

have been presented previously in here can develop competence in the students (Menéndez and Fernández-Río, 2016) helping in the way the ones who had being victimized or preventing this happen. Thereby, it is said that the Personal and Social Responsibility Model can develop in Secondary students the need of competence (Merino-Barrero, Valero-Valenzuela, Belando and Fernández-Río, 2019), as well as other positive psychological consequences (e.g., motivation, *fair play*...). As the model set a successive responsibility levels from respect to help each other and the transference to other contexts, it could done that students feel more competent and avoid with it the victimization behavior.

Finally, about the third basic psychological need, *autonomy*, the results show that *victimization* variable predicts positively the frustration and negatively the satisfaction of this need. The ones who cannot perceived themselves as autonomous are more likely to stand passive in a bully situation (Scholeler et al., 2018). On the contrary, when into the class a student perceives him or herself as autonomous, he or she usually use an absolutely assertive behavior facing the situation using coping strategies and being active to the conflict (Caurcel and Almeida, 2008), decreasing the possibility of victimization behavior apparition. Because of this, bullies see in less autonomous students easy targets to achieve their aims. Research has informed that the victims are usually students with poor management of social relations, students with disabilities or lack in emotional defense, things that are inner linked with low autonomy (Avilés, 2009). This is why is so important to plan student-oriented teaching topics to empower them and give them the responsibility to cop and solve conflicts in an autonomous way facilitating the opportunity to solve the bullying situations independently (Hellison, 2001). Besides, the frustration of the perceived autonomy by the student while the lessons are being conducted, is related to education approaches that produces poor intrinsic motivation (Carrabba and Farmer, 2018). Again, it seems priority to develop the student's autonomy to prevent and / or diminish the negative effects of the victimization. As has been shown previously, pedagogical models as Personal and Social responsibility Model manage to develop in the students the basic psychological need of autonomy (Merino-Barrero et al., 2019), because is just one of the levels of the responsibility that conform the structure of the model. Only if a person feels him or herself autonomous can develop coping strategies for bully situations and not be victimized (Garaigordobil and Martínez-Valderrey, 2014). Thus, these models have to be conducted in the schools.

At last, is worth to say that the data in the current research stay invariant in three different curricular subjects, which reflects the strength of the findings. It has to borne in mind that two of these subjects are taught in the classroom under 'controlled' context where the interaction among students are more restricted while the other one is taught in an 'open' context with more likely interactions not only verbal but also in a corporal level (Jovanović and Zdravković, 2018). Therefore, it can be said that negative and positive links between victimization and the three basic psychological needs occur independently of the curricular context so prevent and/or diminish the negative effects of scholar bullying have to be done from and for the entire educative contexts. Moreover, pedagogical models as Personal and Social Responsibility Model or Cooperative Learning Model can be develop in any subject and achieve benefits from all over them like the ones pointed in advance.

The present study has some limitations that have to be mentioned. Firstly, despite of the wide sample, it is not representative of all possible student body that can be in Spain nor about their socio-economic characteristics nor their geographic localization. Secondly, sampling is intentional for convenience that is, a non-probabilistic sample. With a random stratified sampling or a sample by clusters (probabilistic sample) could

report more reliable results. Thirdly, the analysis is just for three of the Spanish curricular subjects. Finally, as forth limitation, for this research have participated medium socioeconomic level school only, which make the findings extensible merely to this socioeconomic ratio.

The results and the conclusions of this research are fundamental to plan educational intervention programs to tackle the train in values and prosocial learnings from every curricular subjects (Albayrak et al., 2016) like empathy, autonomy or aid behavior. For that, pedagogical contrasted models in the scientific literature could be a key, such as Cooperative Learning Model (Casey and Fernández-Río, 2019), Personal and Social Responsibility Model (Hellison, 2011) or interventions based on dialogic learning, all of this to transform schools into learning communities (Flecha, 2009). These models or a combination of them could reduce negative teenager students' behaviors like aggression and the effects of victimization and being a contribution to solve co-existence problems as develop a positive climate for the personal growth.

Referencias

- Albayrak, S., Yildiz, A., & Erol, S. (2016). Assessing the effect of schoolbullying prevention programs on reducing bullying. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 63, 1-9. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2016.02.005>
- Avilés, J. M. (2009). Victimización percibida y bullying. Factores diferenciales entre víctimas. *Boletín de Psicología*, 95, 7-28.
- Bisquerra, R. (coord.) (2012). *Metodología de la investigación educativa*. Madrid: La Muralla.
- Bondu, R., Rothmund, T., & Gollwitzer, M. (2016). Mutual long-term effects of school bullying, victimization, and justice sensitivity in adolescents. *Journal of Adolescence*, 48, 62-72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.01.007>
- Brechwald, W. A., & Prinstein, M. J. (2011). Beyond homophily: A decade of advances in understanding peer influence processes. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 21, 166-179. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-7795.2010.00721.x>
- Brighi, A., Ortega, R., Pyzalski, J., Scheithauer, H., Smith, P. K., Tsormpatzoudis, C..., & Thompson, J. (2012). *European Bullying Intervention Project Questionnaire (EBIPQ)* (Unpublished manuscript). University of Bologna: Bolonia.
- Byrne, B. M. (2006). *Structural equation modeling with EQS: basic concepts, applications, and programming (multivariate applications)*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Byrne, B. M. (2008). Testing for multigroup equivalence of a measuring instrument: a walk through the process. *Psicothema*, 20(4), 872-882.
- Carrabba, C., & Farmer, A. (2018). The impact of project-based learning and direct instruction on the motivation and engagement of middle school students. *Language Teaching and Educational Research*, 1(2), 163-174.
- Caurcel, M. J., & Almeida, A. (2008). La perspectiva moral de las relaciones de victimización entre iguales: un análisis exploratorio de las atribuciones de adolescentes españoles y portugueses. *European Journal of Education and Psychology*, 1(1), 51-68. <https://doi.org/10.30552/ejep.v1i1.4>
- Casey, A., & Fernández-Río, J. (2019). Cooperative Learning and the affective domain. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation and Dance*, 90(3), 12-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2019.1559671>

- Cepeda-Cuervo, E., Pacheco-Durán, P., García-Barco, L., & Piraquive-Peña, C. (2009). Acoso escolar a estudiantes de educación básica y media. *Revista de Salud Pública*, 10(4), 517-528.
- Cheung, G., & Rensvold, R. (2002). Evaluating goodness-of-fit indexes for testing measurement invariance. *Structural Equation Modelling: A multidisciplinary journal*, 9(2), 233-255. http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/S15328007SEM0902_5
- Cook, C. R., Williams, K., Guerra, N., Kim, T., & Sadek, S. (2010). Predictors of bullying and victimization in childhood and adolescence: a meta-analytic investigation. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 25(2), 65-83. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0020149>
- Fernández-Río, J. (2014). Another step in models-based practice: Hybridizing Cooperative Learning and Teaching for Personal and Social Responsibility. *The Journal of Physical Education, Recreation and Dance*, 85(7), 3-5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2014.937158>
- Forbes, M. K., Fitzpatrick, S., Magson, N. R., & Rapee, N. M. (2019). Depression, anxiety, and peer victimization: bidirectional relationships and associated outcomes transitioning from childhood to adolescence. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 48(4), 692-702. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-018-0922-6>
- Fialho, N., & Bakshi, A. J. (2016). Understanding school bullying: its nature and prevention strategies. *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling*, 44(2), 246-248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03069885.2015.1070635>
- Flecha, R. (2009). Cambio, inclusión y calidad en las comunidades de aprendizaje. *Cultura y Educación*, 21(2), 157-169.
- Garaigordobil, M. (2014). *Programa de intervención para prevenir y reducir el cyberbullying*. Madrid: Pirámide.
- Garaigordobil, M., & Martínez-Valderrey, V. (2014). Efecto del Cyberprogram 2.0 sobre la reducción de la victimización y la mejora de la competencia social en la adolescencia. *Revista de Psicodidáctica*, 19(2), 289-305. <https://doi.org/10.1387/RevPsicodidact.10239>
- Garaigordobil, M., & Martínez-Valderrey, V. (2015). Effects of Cyberprogram 2.0 on “face-to-face” bullying, cyberbullying, and empathy. *Psicothema*, 27(1), 45-51. <https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2014.78>
- Graham, S. (2016). Victims of bullying in schools. *Theory into Practice*, 55(2), 136-144.
- Harbin, S. M., Kelley, M. L., Piscitello, J., & Walker, S. J. (2019). Multidimensional Bullying Victimization Scale: development and validation. *Journal of School Violence*, 18(1), 146-161. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15388220.2017.1423491>
- Hein, V., Koka, A., & Hagger, M. S. (2015). Relationships between perceived teachers' controlling behaviour, psychological need thwarting, anger and bullying behaviour in high-school students. *Journal of Adolescence*, 42, 103-114. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.04.003>
- Hellison, D. (2011). *Teaching responsibility through physical activity* (3rd. ed.). Champaign, Illinois: Human Kinetics.
- Hodges, E. V. E., Malone, M. J., & Perry, D. G. (1997). Individual risk and social risk as interacting determinants of victimization in the peer group. *Developmental Psychology*, 33, 1032-1039. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.33.6.1032>
- Hu, L. T., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cut off criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling*, 6, 1-55. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>
- Huhtiniemi, M., Sääkslahti, A., Watt, A., & Jaakkola, T. (2019). Associations among basic psychological needs, motivation and enjoyment within Finnish physical education students. *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine*, 18(2), 239-247-

- Hutzell, K. L., & Payne, A. A. (2018). The relationship between bullying victimization and school avoidance: an examination of direct associations, protective influences, and aggravating factors. *Journal of School Violence, 17*(2), 210-226. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15388220.2017.1296771>
- Jöreskog, K., & Sörbom, D. (1984). *LISREL VI: Analysis of linear structural relations by maximum likelihood, instrumental variables and least squares methods*. Chicago: National Educational Resources, Inc.
- Jovanović, M., & Zdravković, D. (2018). Nonverbal communication and physical education classes in a social context. *Facta Universitatis: Series Physical Education & Sport, 15*(1), 195-206.
- Juvonen, J., Nishina, A., & Graham, S. (2000). Peer harassment, psychological adjustment, and school functioning in early adolescence. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 92*, 349–359. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.92.2.349>
- Kendrick, K., Jutengren, G., & Stattin, H. (2012). The protective role of supportive friends against bullying perpetration and victimization. *Journal of Adolescence, 35*, 1069-1080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.014>
- Kline, R. B. (2005). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling* (2nd ed.). Nueva York: Guilford Press.
- León-Moreno, C., Martínez-Ferrer, B., Musitu, G., & Moreno, D. (2019). Victimization y violencia escolar: el rol de la motivación de venganza, evitación y benevolencia en adolescentes. *Revista de Psicodidáctica, 24*(2), 88-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psicod.2018.12.001>
- Longo, Y., Alcaraz-Ibáñez, M., & Sicilia, A. (2018). Evidence supporting need satisfaction and frustration as two distinguishable constructs. *Psicothema, 30*(1), 74-81. <https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2016.367>
- Longo, Y., Gunz, A., Curtis, G. J., & Farsides, T. (2016). Measuring need satisfaction and frustration in educational and work contexts: The Need Satisfaction and Frustration Scale (NSFS). *Journal of Happiness Studies, 17*, 295-317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-014-9595-3>
- Magaz, A., Chorot, P., Santed, M., Valiente, R., & Sandín, B. (2016). Evaluación del bullying como victimización: estructura, fiabilidad y validez del Cuestionario de Acoso entre Iguales (CAI). *Revista de Psicopatología y Psicología Clínica, 21*, 77-95.
- Marsh, H. W., & Byrne, B. M. (1993). Confirmatory factor analysis of multitrait-multimethod self-concept data: Between group and within group invariance constraints. *Multivariate Behavioral Research, 28*(3), 313-449.
- Mehdipour, F., Gholamali, M., & Hejazi, E. (2016). Structural modeling on the relationship between basic psychological needs, academic engagement, and test anxiety. *Journal of Education and Learning, 5*(4), 44-52.
- Menéndez, J. I., & Fernández-Río, J. (2016). Violencia, responsabilidad, amistad y necesidades psicológicas básicas: efectos de un programa de Educación Deportiva y Responsabilidad Personal y Social. *Revista de Psicodidáctica, 21*(2), 245-260. <https://doi.org/10.1387/RevPsicodidact.15269>
- Menéndez, J. I., & Fernández-Río, J. (2017). Responsabilidad social, necesidades psicológicas básicas, motivación intrínseca y metas de amistad en educación física. *Retos, 32*, 134-139.
- Menéndez, J. I., & Fernández-Río, J. (2018). Actitudes hacia la violencia y papel importante del alumnado en el aula de educación física. *Revista Complutense de Educación, 29*(4), 1293-1308. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5209/RCED.55352>
- Merino-Barrero, J. A., Valero-Valenzuela, A., Belando, N., & Fernández-Río, J. (2019). Impact of a sustained TPSR program on students' responsibility, motivation,

- sportsmanship and intention to be physically active. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.2019-0022>
- Miranda, R., Oriol, X., Amutio, A., & Ortúzar, H. (2019). Bullying en la adolescencia y satisfacción con la vida: ¿Puede el apoyo de los adultos de la familia y la escuela mitigar este efecto? *Revista de Psicodidáctica*, 24(1), 39-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psicod.2018.07.001>
- Olweus, D. (2005). A useful evaluation design and effects of the Olweus Bullying Prevention Program. *Psychology, Crime & Law*, 11(4), 389–402.
- Ortega, R., del Rey, R., & Casas, J. A. (2016). Evaluar el bullying y el cyberbullying validación española del EBIP-Q y del ECIP-Q. *Psicología Evolutiva*, 22(1), 71-79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pse.2016.01.004>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2002). An overview of self-determination theory: an organismic dialectical perspective. En E. L. Deci y R. M. Ryan (Eds.), *Handbook of self-determination research* (pp. 3–33). Rochester, NY: The University of Rochester Press.
- Sánchez-Oliva, D., Viladrich, C., Amado, D., González-Ponce., I., & García-Calvo, T. (2014). Predicción de los comportamientos positivos en educación física: una perspectiva desde la Teoría de la Autodeterminación. *Revista de Psicodidáctica*, 19(2), 387-406. <https://doi.org/10.1387/RevPsicodidact.7911>
- Schoeler, T., Duncan, L., Ploubidis, G., Cecil, C., & Pingault, J. (2018). Quasi-experimental evidence on short and long-term consequences of bullying victimization: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 144(12), 1229-1246. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/bul0000171.supp>
- Vallerand, R. J. (2001). A hierarchical model of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in sport and exercise. In G. C. Roberts (Ed.), *Advances in motivation in sport and exercise* (pp. 263–319). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Vansteenkiste, M., & Ryan, R. M. (2013). On psychological growth and vulnerability: basic psychological need satisfaction and need frustration as a unifying principle. *Journal of Psychotherapy Integration*, 23(3), 263-280. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/a0032359>
- Van Ryzin, M., & Roseth, C. (2018). Cooperative Learning in middle school: a means to improve peer relations and reduce victimization, bullying and related outcomes. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(8), 1192-1201. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/edu0000265>
- Young-Jones, A., Fursa, S., Byrket, J. S., & Sly, J. S. (2015). Bullying affects more than feelings: the long-term implications of victimization on academic motivation in higher education. *Social Psychology of Education*, 18(1), 185-200.